

CYTOKINE STATUS IN JUVENILE RHEUMATODYNAMIC ARTHRITIS IN CHILDREN OF SCHOOL AGE

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Abstract The aim of this research was to examine the immunological mechanisms of juvenile rheumatoid (JR) arthritis pathogenesis, the importance of cytokines such as IL-8, IL-17A and INF γ in intercellular immune communications and the development of the inflammatory process. Cytokine imbalance leading to a cascade of immunological reactivity disorders subsequently contributes to the development of autoimmunization and chronization of the pathological process in JRA. We studied the change in the production of cytokines depending on seronegative and seropositive forms of JRA. As a result, it was revealed that the level of IL-8, IL-17A was increased in children with a seropositive form. And the level of INF γ was sharply reduced in both groups of examined children with JRA.

Keywords JRA, IL-8, IL-17A, INF γ , seronegative, seropositive.

1. Introduction

According to modern medical data, juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (JRA) is a chronic autoimmune disease characterized by destructive and inflammatory joint damage and occurring in children under 16 years of age. Serious complications such as carditis, interstitial lung disease and serositis occur. Half of the patients have chronic polyarthritis with or without systemic manifestations, progressive osteochondral destruction of the joints and functional insufficiency [1, 5].

Modern research suggests considering JRA not only as a classic autoimmune disease, but also as an autoinflammatory one. However, the full mechanisms of development of this disease remain insufficiently studied [2, 4, 7].

The development and progression of inflammation in rheumatic diseases is caused by autoimmune mechanisms, which are based on a violation of tolerance to one's own antigens, leading to the development of an immune response against normal tissues. This process is mediated by a complex interaction of genetic, immunological factors, various infectious agents and other environmental influences, defects in hormonal and neuroendocrine regulation [3, 6, 11].

The basis of inflammation is a cascade of biochemical and immunological processes, the regulation of which is carried out by a large number of humoral mediators. Among them, cytokines occupy a special place - low-molecular proteins that ensure the process of intercellular interactions [4, 8]. At present, it is the change in the cytokine profile that is considered as a possible trigger mechanism for the development of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis (JRA).

Therefore the main purpose of the study is to study the role of IL-8, IL-17A and INF γ in the development of juvenile rheumatoid arthritis in children and determine their prognostic significance.

2. Materials and methods

The material was collected during 2021-2023 at the Department of Cardiorheumatological Diseases of the Tashkent Pediatric Medical Institute. A total of 106 patients aged 3 to 18 years were examined. All patients underwent a comprehensive clinical examination, including laboratory and instrumental studies. Forty healthy children were examined as a control group for comparison.

To determine the concentration of IL-8, IL-17A, INF γ in the blood serum of the study groups, a three-stage "sandwich" method was used - this is a type of three-phase ELISA "Vector-Best" (Novosibirsk, Russian Federation).

The obtained data were subjected to statistical processing using the Fisher-Student variation statistics method and the Pearson χ^2 criterion.

3. Results and discussions

When analyzing the data obtained by age of children with JRA, we obtained the following results: children aged 3 to 7 years accounted for 11.1% (n=5), aged 7 to 14 years - 57.8% (n=26), aged 14 years and older were 33.3% (n=15). When analyzing gender, a slight predominance of males (53.0%) was revealed, compared to females (47.3%). Pain in the joints of the legs and arms was detected on average in 88.6% (n=40) and 64.4% (n=29) of children, respectively. Local

joint signs of JRA (limited movement, swelling) were found in 77.6% of children. Signs of intoxication (fever, general weakness, loss of appetite, tachycardia, shortness of breath) were observed on average in 39.1%. Neurological disorders (convulsions, capriciousness) were observed in an average of 37.7% of children with JRA. Analysis of somatic diseases revealed that ENT diseases were more common in children with JRA (91.1%). Cardiovascular diseases were observed in 64.4%. Anemia was detected in 53.3% of children with JRA. The incidence of nervous system diseases was 31.1%. Urinary system diseases were also detected in 20.1%, rickets in 13.2%, and dysbacteriosis in 15.6% of children with JRA. Dysmetabolic nephropathy, ophthalmologic disorders, and allergic diseases were detected in an average of 7.74%. TORCH infection was detected in 6.67% of children with the pathology under study.

An important mediator of the inflammatory process in the musculoskeletal system is IL-8 and is considered, according to a number of authors, to be a diagnostic marker of the attack period of rheumatoid arthritis, the level of which is associated with the duration of the disease. It is produced under the influence of tumor necrosis factor, interleukin -1 [3, 8].

When analyzing the IL-8 level in children with juvenile rheumatoid arthritis aged 7-14 years, a reliable increase was found in the group with the seropositive form - 20.9 ± 3.12 pg / ml, which is 1.85 times higher than the values of the control group. In the group with the seronegative form (17.2 ± 2.07 pg / ml), a reliable increase in the IL-8 level by 1.52 times was also observed compared to the control group, but this indicator was 1.2 times lower than the values of the group of children with the seropositive form of JRA ($P \leq 0.05$). (Fig. 1)

Figure 1. IL-8 level in children with JRA aged 7-14 years, pg/ml $P \leq 0.05$

Of particular interest at present is the study of interleukin-17A (IL-17A), which is a proinflammatory cytokine capable of inducing the synthesis of various inflammatory mediators (TNF- α , IL -1, 6), leading to the development of autoimmune reactions. In JIA, a connection has been proven between the development of joint syndrome and hyperproduction of IL -17A [5, 7]

The analysis of IL-17A concentration revealed a reliable increase in its level in both groups, both in the seropositive

form by 2.88 times and in the seronegative form by 2.21 times compared to the control group, with average values of 30.25 ± 4.61 pg/ml and 23.25 ± 2.57 pg/ml, respectively. Also, the IL-17A level in the group of children with JRA with a seropositive form was 1.3 times higher than in the group of children with a seronegative form of this pathology. ($P \leq 0.05$) (Fig. 2)

Figure 2. IL-17A level in children with JRA aged 7-14 years, pg/ml $P \leq 0.05$

A decrease in the body's resistance to microbial infection is associated with an immunosuppressive state, which is expressed in a decrease in the level of interferons, especially interferon γ [9, 11].

In our study, INF γ production was reduced in both groups of examined children with JRA, but the most profound deficiency was observed in the group with the seropositive form with an average value of 11.3 ± 1.93 pg/ml, which is significantly lower by 1.7 times than the values of the control group (19.3 ± 0.83 pg/ml) ($P \leq 0.05$). (Fig. 3)

Figure 3. INF γ level in children with JRA aged 7-14 years, pg/ml $P \leq 0.05$

4. Conclusion

Thus, the conducted study revealed that the level of cytokines IL-8, IL-17A and interferon gamma (INF γ) has significant changes in children with juvenile rheumatoid ar-

thritis (JRA) aged 7 to 14 years. An increase in the level of IL-8 and IL-17A is noted in both children with seropositive and seronegative forms of JRA. At the same time, the production of INF γ is reduced in both groups of children with JRA, the most pronounced deficiency is observed in the group with the seropositive form.

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